

EVALUATION OF TERTIARY ENGLISH PREPARATORY CURRICULUM: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

In this study, which is a case study designed as a program evaluation study, the English language preparatory curriculum of Necmettin Erbakan University, the school of foreign languages was evaluated using the adapted version of the program evaluation model proposed by Bellon and Handler (1982). The aim of this study is to evaluate the English language course of a university preparatory class in terms of a) course aims and objectives, b) course content and materials c) course conduct and d) student assessment and to identify the areas that need improvement regarding these four main elements. In the study, data was obtained through interviews with teachers and the examination of the documents obtained. The results of the study are that the teachers do not find the English lesson effective enough in terms of the four basic elements based on the evaluation model used, that the program is insufficient for students to achieve the course objectives, and that the course materials are not sufficient, it shows that there are

not enough student-centric applications in the course's process and that the assessment is inadequate to effectively measure the success of students. Some of the recommendations that have come as a result of the study are: To ensure that the English course curriculum can be effectively maintained by teachers, a written curriculum must be developed with clear objectives and objectives. In-class materials should be diversified and original materials should be used. In the course process, the methods and techniques of education must be varied to meet the needs of students. Finally, alternative assessment methods should also be used to evaluate the student's performance within the process.

Keywords: Program evaluation, English course evaluation

Introduction

It is one of the most fundamental and important tasks of educational institutions to ensure that individuals are raised in society to adapt to the needs of developing and evolving science and technology. Educational institutions must prepare qualified programs to perform and maintain this function, ensure that these programs are implemented in the most efficient way, and work to continually improve programs (Yüksel ve Sağlam, 2012: 21). It can be said that the most important way to raise individuals who can adapt to the evolving and changing world is to continually evaluate and improve existing education programs. Educational programs aim to ensure individuals develop and keep up with the changing world. However, through educational programs, some behaviors can sometimes be underqualified or sometimes undesirable behaviors can occur. Evaluation is the process that allows the development and improvement of the program by determining which undesired or inadequate results are and what their causes are in such cases, and it provides suggestions and solutions to

eliminate these deficiencies (Uşun, 2016:11). Evaluation of a program from different perspectives has a very important place for decision-making mechanisms, curriculum developers, course material designers and teachers. Program evaluations provide these elements with positive or negative feedback about the different dimensions of the program and enable them to make necessary changes in the development and implementation of the program (Erarslan, 2016).

Ertürk (1991, s.12) defined education as the process of creating a desired change in an individual's behavior through his own life and intentionally. Education, which has the most important place in the development of societies and access to information, can also be carried out effectively thanks to curriculums prepared for specific purposes. Demirel (2009) defined the curriculum as a mechanism of experiences that covers all activities related to the teaching of a lesson that is planned to be taught to individuals at school or out of school. Varış (1997), on the other hand, explained the curriculum as a type of program that generally consists of certain categories of knowledge, focuses on skills and practice in some educational institutions, and aims to gain knowledge and skills in a planned manner in line with the objectives of the education program (Stufflebeam, 1994). When we narrow the evaluation process to program evaluation; The processes of systematically providing information about services such as workshops, seminars, trainings applied in different sectors, an education or training program can be defined as program evaluation (Gredler, 1995). Curriculum evaluation process in education can be expressed as the process of determining to what extent the programs put into practice in schools reach their determined goals (Özdemir, 2009).

It is clear that program evaluation efforts are one of the most important parts of the process to ensure the continuity of the curriculum and to identify its

deficiencies and eliminate them. For the first time, Scriven (1967) divided curriculum evaluation into two groups as formative and summative evaluation. If the primary purpose of evaluation is to identify the deficiencies of the program and to ensure that the program is developed as a result, this is called the formative program evaluation approach. Unlike formative program evaluation, which aims to improve the program, summative curriculum evaluation practices provide information and support for deciding on issues such as whether to accept the current program or continue with this program. Since the views, values, goals and preferences of program evaluators differ, there are also various approaches (such as Goal, Management and Expert-Oriented) in program evaluation (Fitzpatrick, Sanders and Worthen, 2004). The different approaches and models mentioned can be used directly or adapted for course or program evaluation (Yel, 2009:20).

When the literature was searched, the following studies were found at the secondary school level; Evaluation of the secondary school English curriculum developed in 2012 with the Stake's suitability-probability assessment model (Kaya, 2018), Evaluation of the vocational school English curriculum using the context, input, process, product (CIPP) model (Ödemiş, 2018), Evaluation of the 9th Grade High School English Curriculum According to the Principles of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (Yüce, 2018), Evaluation of the Effectiveness of English Lessons in Sivas Anatolian High Schools (Yel, 2009). The program evaluation studies carried out at the undergraduate level are as follows; Evaluation Study of the Preparatory Program Main Course Curriculum : A Case Study (Mutlu, 2018), Evaluation of Yıldız Technical University Preparatory Education Program (Akpur, 2017), Evaluation of the Eastern Mediterranean University English Language Education Department Curriculum (Zorba, 2015), Ankara University Preparatory School Evaluation of the Curriculum with the CIPP Model (Tunç, 2010), Evaluation of

Language Development Courses in the Eastern Mediterranean University English Language Teaching Department Undergraduate Program: Case Study (Erozan, 2005). Considering the last 10 years in Turkey, the above-mentioned program evaluation studies have been carried out and as a result of these evaluation studies, the outputs of the programs that have not been realized or that have been realized as insufficient have been determined and suggestions and solutions have been presented for the development and improvement of these programs. It was thought that the evaluation of the English preparatory curriculum with the Bellon and Handler (1982) program evaluation model would provide a different vision, and the aim of the research was expressed as "The evaluation of the English preparatory class curriculum of the School of Foreign Languages in terms of the curriculum elements". For this purpose, answers were sought for the following sub-objectives;

1. What are the suggestions of the teachers to improve the Course Aims And Objectives Component of the curriculum?

2. What are the suggestions of the teachers to improve the Course Content and Materials Component of the curriculum?

3. What are the suggestions of the teachers to improve the Course Conduct Component of the curriculum?

4. What are the suggestions of the teachers to improve the Student Assessment of the curriculum?

Methodology

The research is a case study designed as a program evaluation study by using interview technique in qualitative research method. In the study, it was aimed to evaluate a state university preparatory class English curriculum and Bellon and Handler (1982) program evaluation model was used. Bellon and Handler (1982)

model allows to evaluate in detail the objectives and aims of the course, course content and materials, course teaching and finally the evaluation of the student, which are four focus areas, and provides the opportunity to reach suggestions for improvement and development of the program by analyzing the current situation of the program. . For these reasons, it was chosen for use in this study. The researcher made some changes to the Bellon and Handler (1982) model in order to adapt it to the current situation and conditions. The interviews with the teachers were evaluated using the content analysis technique and direct quotations were included in the study.

The study group of the research consists of 4 teachers working in the preparatory class English program of the School of Foreign Languages in a state university in the 2017-2018 academic year.

In the research, qualitative data were obtained with a semi-structured interview form and the documents collected about the program were used. In the interviews, semi-structured interview forms were used in order to obtain deeper and richer information about the teachers' views and suggestions on the four focal points of the course, the objectives and aims of the course, the course content and materials, the teaching of the course and the evaluation of the student. The semi-structured interview form was adapted from Erozan (2005) and some questions were deleted and some were combined for the purposes of the current study.

Findings

1. Course Aims And Objectives

In the interviews with the teachers, Teacher A stated that the objectives such as effective communication, creative thinking, critical thinking and collaborative work, which every individual should have in the 21st century, should be added to the objectives of the current English lesson curriculum. He also stated that critical media literacy skills should be added to the current

objectives of the English course. He said that writing in daily and simple genres should be developed and effective written communication in more academic genres such as comparison, explanation, cause-effect explanation and discussion should be added as the writing skill objectives in the lessons. He stated that students should be able to develop their note-taking skills and that they should be able to understand which concepts and points in the text are important while listening or reading a text, and that these statements should be noted effectively. Other teachers made suggestions such as:

“Actually, there is no problem with the existing targets when considered fundamentally, but there are disruptions in reaching the targets due to the problems in implementation and because students at different learning levels have to follow the same curriculum. I believe that the desired objectives can be reached more effectively by classifying the students according to their levels and focusing on skill lessons. In addition, while students reach their current goals in reading and writing skills more easily, they cannot get rid of the cliché "I understand but I cannot speak", and sometimes they cannot even understand what is being said or what they are listening to. This shows that the listening skill goals are not fully achieved. In this context, I believe that skill courses should be included in the curriculum as separate courses and should be supported by creative activities.” (Teacher C)

Objectives such as developing their own effective note-taking strategies and techniques, participating in discussions effectively and making effective presentations should be added to

the objectives of the English course. In addition, activities directly related to real life should be used abundantly by teachers in order to achieve these goals. ' (Teacher D)

2. Course Content and Materials

All of the interviewed teachers stated that only the textbook was insufficient as a course material and that different materials should be used in addition to the course book. The interviewed teachers also offered the following suggestions. Regarding the content of the English course and the materials used, the course content is mostly composed of the book, which is the main source, and that the inadequacy of this book also causes the course content to be inadequate. It has been stated that there is a need for an extra course material to support writing skills, especially in order to develop students' writing skills more effectively. In order to support reading skills, English books suitable for students' levels should also be integrated into the course content, and real-life materials that students can comment on and think about should also be used effectively in the classroom.

3. Course Conduct

In the interviews with the teachers, it was seen that all of the teachers thought that the English lesson should be taught in a student-centered manner and that activities should be included in the lessons to keep the participation and motivation of the students high.

Our students may seem like adults now, but I think they still need action, conversation and fun in class. Therefore, interaction and communication should be high in the teaching

of the English lesson, and activities that encourage students to think and creativity should be used. (*Teacher A*)

Lecturing by sticking to a book during the lesson makes the lesson monotonous from time to time, and for this reason, we should make the lesson more effective by including more technological opportunities in the lesson. More drama-style activities should be used in the lessons. These will make the lesson more fun and increase the motivation of the student. (*Teacher B*)

While teaching English, I think that I provide enough activity variety for students to learn more effectively by actively using games, competitions and group activities in my lessons as well as the textbook. I usually pay attention to the equality of the teacher and student roles in the lessons and try to ensure that the students take an active role. (*Teacher A*)

Sometimes I spend a lot of time to finish the chapters of the textbook and therefore I am not able to implement extra activities for the students. I am usually in control of the lessons and try to give feedback to the students as much as possible. (*Teacher B*)

4. Student Assessment

In the interviews with the teachers, when the question "How do you think the success of the students in the preparatory class should be measured?", the interviewed teachers expressed their suggestions as follows;

First of all, one should not depend only on achievement tests. Their in-class participation should definitely be taken into account, and their measurements should be provided through different methods. Rather than measuring students' performance and seeing their level or what they have achieved, we should focus on methods where we can provide instant feedback to students and offer suggestions and solutions for their improvement. For example, in-class presentations, debates, 1-minute short descriptive speeches, partner dialogues, group work for writing, everything should be used as an effective measurement tool for all activities in the classroom. Teachers should keep checklists and these lists should be actively involved in the evaluation process. For example; It is necessary to apply checklists and lesson observation forms that will provide concrete data to the teacher in many subjects such as observing the motivation and interest of the student, determining whether he fulfills his homework responsibility, evaluating his role in group work, determining whether he understands the instructions given, and identifying his missing and strong points. (*Teacher A*).

Since language learning is a process, these exams are effective, but their in-class performance is also very important and should be considered. Performance assignments and presentations should also be taken into account when evaluating student achievement. ' (*Teacher B*)

In the evaluation process of students, physical environments where students can be found in real learning environments should be provided in addition to the current exams. They should be asked to do live chats or writing exercises using English as the language of communication through chat programs. I believe it would be beneficial to use sound recordings or written outputs of these as well. ' (Teacher C)

“In addition to the current exams, students should be given projects to measure their performance. Also, I think that students' success can be measured more effectively by asking open-ended questions rather than multiple-choice questions in exams. ' (Teacher D)

Discussion

1. Course Aims And Objectives

As a result of the document analysis carried out by the researcher, it was determined that there was no existing written curriculum in the preparatory class of the institution with the goals and objectives of the course. It has been determined that the English course is planned in line with the selection of textbooks prepared in accordance with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). An effective curriculum enables teachers, students, administrators, and other elements of the system to maintain a quality education through a measurable plan. Curriculum is the documentation that clearly states the learning outcomes, standards and basic skills expected to be acquired and demonstrated by students (Glen, 2018). Yel (2009) stated in his study that the goals and objectives of the course are very important and that when

teachers have clear information about the goals and objectives of the course, they can prepare lesson plans more effectively and efficiently in order to achieve these goals and objectives. In this way, he stated that the current course would be more satisfying for the students and could effectively meet the expectations and needs of the students. As a result, it is seen that it is essential for the institution to have a curriculum in accordance with its own philosophy and goals for the English course to continue the English courses more effectively.

In the interviews with the teachers, it was mentioned that the students did not improve their language skills as much as they expected, but they stated that they made a certain progress in grammar. Teachers stated that one of the main objectives of the English lesson should be to be able to use English fluently and effectively. It is seen that the teachers are not satisfied with the point that the students have reached in expressing themselves in English verbally and they expect them to be in a better place as a result of the English preparatory class. Although the objectives of the lesson include the development of these skills, the reason why these objectives cannot be achieved sufficiently may be that the practices in the English lessons of the teachers are not sufficient to reach these objectives. Yel (2009) also reached a conclusion in the same direction about the inability to reach the speaking skill goals of the English course sufficiently in his study.

2. Course Content and Materials

While the teachers stated that it is not necessary to stick to the textbook only for the English lesson, they also said that all teachers should also use videos, movies, storybooks or texts obtained from different sources in the lessons. As a result of the teacher interviews, it is seen that all the teachers who participated in the interviews agreed that the main book of the course alone is insufficient and

that there is a need for a variety of activities and materials in the lessons. In addition, it was stated by the teachers of the course that additional textbooks that focus on independent reading-writing and listening-speaking skills should be used.

3. Course Conduct

Teachers stated that the lessons are generally taught under teacher control and teacher-centered. The fact that the teachers stated that activities such as group activities in which students will take an active role should be applied more in the classroom supports this situation. It was stated by the teachers that different activities such as group work, bilateral dialogue work and games should be used during the lessons. Yel (2009), Erozan (2005) and Mutlu (2018) also concluded in their studies that students need a variety of activities in their English lessons.

4. Student Assessment

When the teacher interviews were examined, they stated that the students generally stated that they had a positive attitude towards the evaluation process, that some types of questions asked especially in the midterm exams did not match the types of questions they had studied in their classes, and that this situation prevented the success of the students from being measured correctly. While they stated that open-ended questions should be used instead of multiple-choice questions used in exams, they stated that student achievement could be measured effectively.

Teachers stated that students' in-class performances should also be taken into account in the evaluation process, rather than using only quizzes, midterms and final exams in the evaluation. Teachers stated that the use of presentations and project assignments in the evaluation of the student can effectively evaluate the student's performance during the year. The results obtained on the use of

alternative assessment methods such as project assignments and presentations in the evaluation of students in English lessons provide consistency with the results of Erozan (2005) on this subject.

The teachers stated that there was 5 hours between the speaking exams and the written exams in the midterm exams, and that waiting at school during this period affected the performance of the students badly. In this case, minimizing the time difference between the sections of the exam held on the same day would be good in terms of measuring the success of the students exactly.

Conclusion and further research

Recommendations for Current Practice

The following suggestions, based on the results of the current study, can be applied in the coming years in order to develop and improve the missing and failing aspects of the English preparatory class, and to continue it more effectively.

1. A needs analysis can be done to determine the needs and expectations of the students studying in the preparatory class. As a result of the needs analysis, a written curriculum of the institution can be developed for the preparatory class English course. Thanks to a curriculum in which the goals and objectives of the course are written, teachers who will be aware of these goals and purposes can choose more appropriate and effective teaching methods and techniques, the materials to be chosen for the course can be determined more useful, and measurement tools can be developed that can measure students' success more effectively.

2. Diversity should be provided in the materials used in the lessons, and written, visual and audio materials related to the current issues that attract the attention of the students should be used more in the lessons.
3. Activities such as group work, mutual discussions and bilateral dialogue activities that will enable students to be more active in the learning process should be used more frequently in the lessons.
4. Extra textbooks based on reading, writing, listening and speaking skills should be used in addition to the current textbook, although it contains a section on each skill.
5. Emphasis should be placed on communicative activities that will encourage students to use English more orally.
6. Materials such as podcasts, songs and videos should be used more frequently in classrooms to improve students' listening skills.
7. Instead of being teacher-centered, lessons should be carried out more student-centered through activities in which the student will take an active role in the learning process.
8. Activities such as assignments, projects and presentations given to prevent students from studying only for exams should also be included in the evaluation process.
9. The effect of only 5% of the student's performance throughout the year on the success score should be increased and its importance should be increased in the student's performance in the lessons.
10. In exams, the types of questions that students encounter in class should be used instead of the types of questions they do not encounter in the lessons.

11. In exams consisting of more than one section (midterm exams), the time between sections should be kept as short as possible and it should be prevented from being affected by external factors that will affect the student's success.

12. The quizzes, midterms and final exams used to measure students' success should be reviewed and necessary improvements should be made to measure students' current knowledge and skills more effectively.

Recommendations for Future Research

The following suggestions can be taken into consideration in future program evaluation studies.

1. In this study, teachers' opinions were evaluated. In future research, different data can be obtained by evaluating the opinions of the managers of the institutions.

2. Classroom observations can also be used as data collection tools in program evaluation studies.

3. The evaluation model used in the research can be used in the evaluation of other courses.

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